

ISSN: 2456-5474

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/68367

VOL.- X , ISSUE- V June - 2025

Innovation The Research Concept

Agronomic Practices of Mustard

Paper Id : 20327 Submission Date : 2025-06-10 Acceptance Date : 2025-06-21 Publication Date : 2025-06-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16728597

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Hemant Singh

Teacher
Madhyamic Education Department
Government High School
Kanjias, Musafirkhana, India,

Veena Tiwari

Retired Associate Professor
Department Of Botany
P.P.N. Degree College
Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh

Satish R. Subhedar

Principal Investigator - D.S.T.
Dept. Of Science And Technology

Abstract An important oil seed plant, mustard (*Brassica juncea*) was studied to determine the best agronomic practices for its growth and oil production. This study was carried out in Bithoor, near Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh. Modifying the ICAR guidelines, innovative fertilizer combinations of 80-40-80 kg/ha NPK (F3) and another combination using 50% organic and 50% inorganic fertilizers (F4) was used. The innovative plant geometry of 75 cm x 75 cm was used. It was found that, while the F4 combination was best for vegetative growth, the F3 combination proved more suitable for productivity.

Keywords Agronomic, Practices, Mustard

Introduction

It is well known that mustard is an important oil seed plant of India. However, the methodology farmers generally practices for growing mustard (*B. Juncea*) which does not permit the best growth and oil productivity. In the present study, innovated methodologies have been used to study the most flexible combinations of plant geometry and fertilizer doses. For the purposes of this paper, we have varied the fertilizers but have used the best plant spacing.

Objective of study

To find out best agronomic practices for Indian mustard crop.

Review of Literature

Ahmad and Abdin (2000) suggested that balanced N and S supply should be maintained for both quantity and quality of oil of *Brassica* genotypes.

Kumar and Yadav(2007) conducted an experiment to find out the optimum dose of phosphorus and sulphur for Indian mustard. A significant response of crop was observed up to 26.2 kg P and 30 kg S/ha in seed and stover yields.

Meena et al. (2006) clearly noticed the beneficial effect of use of Zn and Fe enriched FYM over straight Zn and Fe application as a direct effect in mustard.

Premi et al.(2012) concluded that *Sesbania* as green manure and incorporation of mustard straw improved carbon sequestration potential of the soil, better partial factor productivity and production efficiency .

Verma et al.(2023) concluded that zinc and sulphur affect significantly on the growth , yield attributes and seed yield of Indian mustard.

Methodology Indian mustard is an annual herb that is used as an oilseed crop. Its botanical name is *Brassica juncea* L. (Czernj. and Cosson. *Brussica juncea* is an annual herb, branched. 90-180 cm high. Stem - Erect, much branched. Leaf - Leaves are stalked, glabrous or

hairy. Inflorescence - Corymbose raceme. Flower- Tetramerous, bracteates, pedicellate, complete hypogynous. Calyx - Four, polysepalous, green in colour. Corolla - Four, Polypetalous, Cruciform, yellow in colour. Androecium - Six Stamens, Polyandrous, tetradynamous in two whorls. Gynoecium - Bicarpellary, Syncarpous, ovary superior. Fruit - Siliqua Seed - Numerous, minute, ex-albuminous Although we had used the ICAR recommended plant geometry of 15 cm x 45 cm, we found that when plants were grown so close together, they were unable to grow properly. Hence we used the innovated spacing of 75 cm x 75 cm. All the results here are on the basis of this plant to plant distance. The results pertain to three years of work, viz, 2017-2018, 2018- 2019 and 2019-2020. The parameters considered were plant height, 60 DAS in cm, primary branches per plant, secondary and tertiary branches per plant, average leaf area in cm², length of the pod (cm) , weight of seed per plot (g), seed yield (kg/ha), oil content (%), oil yield (Kg/ha) and test weight of 1000 seeds (g). Where fertilizers were concerned, we maintained a pair added fertilizers (F1) and three more combinations were (F2) 80-40-40 kg/ha NPK (Urea, SSP, MOP). However, we have used two innovated doses, viz, F3 (80-40 - 80 kg / ha NPK) and F4 (50% organic : 40 kg/ha FYM 20 kg/ha neem cake and 40 kg/ha biofertiliser plus 50% Inorganic - 40-20-40 kg/ha NPK)

Result and Discussion

The plant height and number of primary branches per plant increased from F1 to F4 in all three years. Also the average number of secondary and tertiary branches per plant increased in the same manner. The average leaf area and length of pod showed a similar trend. However the other parameters showed a different trend. It was found that the innovative fertilizer administration of 80 kg/ha nitrogen as urea plus 40kg/ha of phosphorus as single super phosphate plus 80 kg/ha potassium as MOP was more effective than other fertilizer combination in production attributes such as seed yield, oil yield, oil content, test weight of 1000 seeds, weight of seeds per plot.

The vegetative parameters have shown an upward trend where 50% organic and 50% inorganic fertilizer (innovated F4) were used and because of this, the same trend exhibited by the straw yield. Verma et al (2023) have recorded a maximum plant height of 161.2 cm using zinc and sulphur supplements, where in our study, the maximum plant height has been recorded as 177.00 cm in third year of study in the innovated fertilizer combination (F4). Similarly, they have recorded the number of primary branches as 8.5 compared to our 13.5 in the same year and fertilizer compared to our 13.5 in the same year and fertilizer combination and their secondary branches have been shown at 14.8. We have studied secondary as well as tertiary branches recorded at 58.75. All in all, it was observed that the innovative 50% organic and 50% inorganic fertilizer combination (F4) was most effective in vegetative parameters, Among the reproductive and production parameters, the length of the pod was highest in F4, but other parameters, viz, seed yield, oil yield, oil content, test weight of 1000 seeds and weight of seeds per plot were highest in the innovative fertilizer combination of 80-40-80 kg/ha NPK. However the straw yield was highest in F4 that contains 50% organic and 50% inorganic fertilizers. Since straw yield is a function of vegetative growth indirectly, this was in accordance with the maximum values of vegetative parameters in the same fertilizer combination. However the reproductive and productivity parameters showed maximum values in the F3 fertilizer combination. Although Swaminathan had advocated the aggressive use of NPK for the development of high yielding dwarf varieties of wheat during the Green revolution he later admitted that these fertilizers were inadequate in repairing the depleted soil. Farmers, before this used farmyard manure ploughing, hoeing etc. were done with the help of bullocks and not tractors. Their faeces also fertilized the soil. Unfortunately, their chemical analysis and that of the farmyard manure, could not be done accurately, hence were not acceptable, in Western world. Now, however a new word has been coined organic farming where the ancient methods of fertilizers have begun to be used. More work is required to scientifically replenish the depleted soil with all the macro and micro nutrients.

S.No.	Parameters	Fertilizer											
		2017-18				2018-19				2019-20			
		S3 F1	S3 F2	S3 F3	S3 F4	S3 F1	S3 F2	S3 F3	S3 F4	S3 F1	S3 F2	S3 F3	S3 F4
1.	Plant Height 60 DAS (in cm)	128.41	141.83	142.17	144.86	125.75	148.50	156.83	174.00	143.75	149.16	150	177.00
2.	Primary branches per plant	9.75	11.50	11.50	12.50	9.25	11.50	12.50	13.50	11.0	12.50	13.00	13.50
3.	Sec. & tertiary branches per plant	22.75	29.75	34.50	41.75	34.50	49.75	50	51.25	29.50	55.00	55.75	58.75
4.	Average leaf area (cm ²)	375	550	580	588	342	580	585	607	348	640	668	685
5.	Length of pod (cm)	5.65	5.25	5.75	5.80	4.92	5.42	5.75	5.90	5.45	5.50	5.85	5.85
6.	Seed weight/plant (g)	304	316.01	371	381	305	315	348	370	322	750	781	800
7.	Seed yield (kg/ha)	405.33	421.33	494.66	507.99	406.66	419.99	463.99	499.33	429.33	1000	1041.33	1066.67
8.	Straw yield (kg/ha)	311.10	395.54	440	444.44	311.10	400	444.44	466.66	333.33	633.33	688.88	693.33
9.	Oil content (%)	36.05	37.64	38.78	38.61	31.10	31.69	34.81	33.54	35.12	34.92	38.50	36.05
10.	Oil yield (kg/ha)	146.12	162.67	191.77	191.20	128.87	140.86	171.72	148.03	150.78	360.50	400.91	372.42
11.	Test Weight 1000 seed (g)	4	4.07	4.20	4.12	3.97	4.00	4.32	4.20	3.88	4.60	5.40	4.90

Conclusion

We can conclude by pointing out that the innovative fertilizer combination of 80-40-80 kg/ha NPK are most suitable for the productivity of Brassica juncea. On the other hand a combination of organic and inorganic fertilizers is best for the vegetative growth of the plant.

References

- Ahmad, A. and Abdin, M.Z. (2000). Interaction effect of sulfur and nitrogen on the oil and protein contents and on the fatty acid profiles of oil in the seeds of rapeseed (*Brassicacampastris* L.) and mustard (*B. Juncea* L. Czern & Coss). *Journal of Agronomy and crop science*. 185 (1). 49.
- Arthamwar, D.N. Shelke, V.B. and Ekshinge B.S. (1996). Effect of nitrogen and phosphorus on yield attributes seed and oil yield of Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*). *Indian Journal of Agronomy*. 41(2) : 282-285.
- Chauhan, D.R. and Paroda, S. (1995). Response of Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*) to bio-fertilizer and nitrogen. *Indian Journal of Agronomy* 40(1): 86-90.
- Chauhan, D.R., Ram, M. and Singh, Ishwar (2002). Response of Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*) to irrigation and fertilization with various sources and levels of sulphur. *Indian Journal of Agronomy*. 47 (3): 422-426.
- Chouksey H., Sardana V. and Sharma P. (2016). Influence of phosphorus application on seed yield quality and phosphorus uptake pattern of Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*) cultivars. *Journal of oilseeds Research*, 33 (3) : 163-167.
- Goswami, G. and Sinhamahaptra, S.P. (2008). Effect of siliqua orientation of seed yield and some yield attributes in Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*). *Indian Journal of Agri sciences*. 78 (6) : 554-556.
- Kumar H. and yadav, D.S. (2007). Effect of phosphorous and sulphur levels on growth, yield and quality of Indian mustard (*B. Juncea*) cultivars. *Indian Journal of Agronomy*. 52(2): (154- 157).
- Lallu and Kumar, M. (2012). Variability in Biochemical and Physiological parameters of mustard (*Brassica juncea* L. Czern and Coss). genotypes under rainfed and irrigated conditions. *Indian J. Agric. Biochemical* 25(2): 129-133.
- Meena, M.C., Patel K.P. and Rathod, D.D. (2006). Effect of zinc and Fe enriched FYM application on mustard, *Brassica juncea* (L). Czern and Coss. yield and quality. *J. Oilseeds Res*. 23(7) : 331-336.
- Premi, O.P., Rathor, S.S. Shekhawat, K, Kandpal, B.K. and Chauhan, J.S. (2012). Sustainability of fallow - Indian mustard (*B. Juncea*) system as influenced by green manure, mustard straw cycling and fertilizer application. *Indian Journal of Agronomy*. 57 (3) : 229-234.
- Mishra A., Gupta H . Mishra U.S., Sirothia P. Darwai P. Interaction effect of sulphur and NPK on growth parameters and yield of mustard *International journal of plant & soil science* 2023, 35(15) : 138-144.
- Singh R.S., Chaudhary C.S. and Mukharji U. 2018,. Effect of date of sowing and crop geometry on yield, oil content and economics of Indian mustard (*Brassica juncea*). L.) *International journal of current microbiology and applied sciences*, 7 : 4599- 4601.
- Verma,A. , Singh , A.K. , Jatav, A.L., Verma, V.K., Pratap , M., Chaudhary,B.K. ,& Kumar, D.(2023). Effect of zinc and sulphur on growth, yield attributes and seed yield of Indian mustard [*Brassica juncea* (L.)]. Czern &Coss]. *International Journal of Plant and soil science*,35(21),161-169.